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Research Article

Formulation and Evaluation of Antimicrobial Herbal Soap by Using Turmeric, Orange peel powder & Neem

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ABSTRACT

Bacterial infections are most common in human. The herbs are known to possess various potential like anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial and anti-fungal properties which are explored for ages and incorporated into various forms, for human use. One such usage is formulation of herbal soap that are used not only for treating microbial infections, but also for using it on daily basis. Some herbal plant extracts and their oils were found to have antibacterial activity. The prepared formulation was evaluated for various phytochemical parameters for which good characteristics were observed. Effectiveness and easy availability of plants with less or no side effect and economic to consumers.

INTRODUCTION

The herbal soap is a type of herbal cosmetics. The herbal cosmetics are preparation containing phytochemicals from variety of botanical sources, which influence function of skin and also provide nutrients necessary for healthy skin and body. In the cosmetic preparation natural herbs, products and some extract used for their aromatic value are called as herbal cosmetics. Herbal cosmetics are made up by the natural ingredients, various plant and seeds extracts. They are neither have adverse effect nor allergic responses. They can easily blend on the skin. Compared with the other beauty products in small quantities it is more effective.

They are widely available and present in wide range of plants. popular advantages of herbal cosmetics are they are non-toxic in nature and they having tendency to reduce allergic reactions. Plant having one or more of its parts having substance that can be used for treatment of disease are called medicinal plants. Medicinal component derived from plants are widely famous due to their safety, east availability and low cost. Herbal medicines may include whole part of plant or mostly leaves, root, bark, seeds and flowers of the plant. Plants contain phytochemicals such as alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, terpenoids, essential oils and phenolic compound. Soap is a mixture of sodium salts of

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various naturally occurring fatty acids. The most commercial soaps contain chemicals that can be harmful to the skin and using a natural herbal soap can be a good alternative. Herbal soap is a natural alternative to conventional soap that is often made by using botanical herbs and plant – based ingredients. Herbal soaps are also prepared by medicinal plants which contain anti-ageing, anti-microbial, anti-oxidant which are beneficial for treatment of skin related problems, disease, injury etc. This preparation possesses anti-microbial properties and are administered topically and available to apply in various forms like creams, gels, soaps, ointments etc. Herbal soaps are effective in curing different skin problems. The herbs infused in these soaps have therapeutic and healing characteristics that offers specific benefits to the skin such as nourishment, strength, healing and moisturizing. These soaps also contain glycerin which is generally not used in commercial soaps. Glycerin helps in retaining the moisture in skin thereby making these soaps for dry skin conditions. Herbal soaps are natural product mostly found in the treatment of almost all types of skin related problems also it uses to enhance beauty.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials used for anti-microbial herbal soap are as follows-

- Sodium hydroxide.
- Neem oil.
- Turmeric.
- Ritha.
- Orange peel powder.
- Steric acid.
- Glycerine.

- Triethanolamine.
- Distilled water.

Procedure For Preparation of Anti-Microbial Herbal Soap

Cold Process Method:

Three herbal soap formulations (B1, B2 & B3) were prepared by cold press method as given in table no.1.

- The soap formulation base was prepared by taking sodium hydroxide and dissolve in distilled water and the solution was heated at 70°C in a beaker.
- Then in another beaker glycerine, orange peel powder and ritha were taken into 250ml beaker and placed it on water bath with stirring it and heated the mixture to 60°C.
- Once this heat is attained steric acid was added and heated at 68°C by slowly added the lye (sodium hydroxide) solution with stirring it until the mixture become transparent.
- After this required quantity of herbal oil and extract were mixed to the above solution.
- Volume was made up to 100ml by adding remaining distilled water. The solution was kept undisturbed for a one hour at 68°C.
- At the last few drops of jasmine oil was also added to impart aroma of prepared soap. After one-hour triethanolamine was added slowly.
- The soap solution was cooled to 62- 64°C. Then the prepared soap mixture was poured into mould.
- The mould was kept aside for 3-4 days for the solidification of the soap.

Fig. Materials

Table 1: Formulation and Anti-microbial Herbal Soap

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Formulation		
		B1	B2	B3
1.	Sodium hydroxide	29.6 gm	1.6 gm	1.6 gm
2.	Stearic acid	-	10 gm	13 gm
3.	Neem oil	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml
4.	Turmeric	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml
5.	Glycerine	-	6.25 gm	6.25 gm
6.	Ritha	15 gm	20 gm	25 gm
7.	Triethanolamine	-	5 ml	2 ml
8.	Orange peel powder	19 gm	19 gm	15 gm
9.	Jasmine oil	1 ml	1 ml	1 ml
10.	Distilled water	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.

Prepared the 25ml of the 1% of soap solution and transferred it into 100ml measuring cylinder. Then cylinder was shaken 10 times. The volume of foam was recorded at one minute for 4 to 5 minutes.

5. Foam hight:

0.5 gm of the soap sample was taken and dispersed in 25ml of distilled water. Then transferred it into 100ml measuring cylinder, the volume was made up to 50ml with water. 25 strokes were given and stand till aqueous volume was measured up to 50ml and measured the foam height, above the aqueous volume.

6. pH determination:

The pH determination test was performed for all the batches of formulation. Each formulation of the prepared soap solution was dissolved in 20ml of distilled waster and tested

with the help of a digital pH meter. The measurement of pH for all formulation batches was done by previously calibrated pH meter.

7. Alcohol insoluble matter:

5gm of prepared soap was taken in a conical flask and added 50ml warm ethanol and shaken vigorously to dissolve the soap. The solution was filtered through a tarred filter paper with 20ml of warm ethanol and dried at 105°C for 1hrs. the weight of dried paper with residue was taken.

8. Anti-microbial test:

The prepared soap was subjected to anti-microbial screening by the agar well diffusion standard cup plate method. Organisms used were E. coli, S. aureus and P. aeruginosa. One gram of soap was mixed with 5ml of sterile water.

Table 2: Physiochemical parameters of Herbal Soap Formulation.

Sr. No.	Parameter	Formulation F1	Formulation F2	Formulation F3
1.	Appearance	Good	Good	Good
2.	Colour	Brownish	Yellowish	Yellowish
3.	Odour	Pleasant	Pleasant	Pleasant
4.	pH Determination	7.2	7.1	7.4
5.	Foam retention (min)	3.2	3.4	3.2
6.	Foam hight (cm)	3.3	3.0	3.3
7.	Weight determination	100gm	100gm	100gm
8.	Alcohol insoluble matter (%)	16	19	15

Fig. Prepared Anti-Microbial Soap.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The evaluation of anti-microbial herbal soap was performed successfully. The prepared herbal soap was shown in figure no. 1. The physiochemical parameters for herbal soap formulation F1, F2, F3 such as colour, odour, appearance and pH were determined. The formulation has a yellowish colour with an aromatic odour and good appearance. The pH was found to be in the range of 7.3. healthy skin has pH of 5.4 to 5.9 and the

prepared formulation pH was found to be neutral in nature and doesn't cause any irritation to skin. Other parameters like foam height, foam retention was also performed and showed good results. Alcohol insoluble matter was also evaluated successfully which was found to be 15-19%, it indicated that the prepared soaps were free from non- soap ingredients. The anti-microbial activity of herbal soaps was studied. The results obtained from the studies were shown photographically in table no.

Table 3: Antimicrobial Test for Herbal Soaps

Sr.no.	Formulation code	Zone of inhibition (mm)		
		Microorganisms		
		P. aeruginosa	Microorganisms S. aureus	E. coil
1.	F1	12	14	13
2.	F2	15	18	16

Figure 2: Zone of Inhibition for F2 formulation

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

In the present work, antimicrobial herbal soaps were prepared, with suitable size and shape, thickness, weight, and with good foam producing ability. Herbal soaps of neem and turmeric were prepared for their anti-bacterial activity for the treatment of pimples, acne and scars. Two different formulations F1 and F2 were prepared by

cold press method and the formulations were characterized for different evaluation parameters like clarity, colour, and odour, size, and shape, thickness, weight, pH in which they exhibited satisfactory results. The herbal soap showed a good appearance with pink colour and with a pleasant aromatic smell and showed good anti-bacterial properties. Based on the study it can be concluded that herbal products can be effectively

formulated in the form of medicated herbal soaps by using cold process technique with excellent anti-bacterial properties.

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